

Three component accelerometer signal processing for WARN

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Changed:

4.3, using the projection from Eq. 28 all three signal components should be used for the P- and S-wave STA/LTA detectors, A.R. 20160307

5.3, the step-size $\delta a = 0.1 \text{ cm/s}^2$ in the JMA algorithm is too large for pure noise observations. It should be in the order of (possibly fractions of) μg (earth' acceleration). A.R. 20170831

5.3, currently JMA a_0 is only used in a heart-beat message and is supposed to represent current noise levels. It is then not necessary to use the FIR-filter from section 2.1 but rather remove bias by applying a high-pass filter (see 2.2) to the signal. A.R. 20170131

4.1, the Octave/Matlab code example actually would compute the inclination in radians, which is in contradiction of equation 29. A.R. 20190523

1 Overview

This document attempts a detailed mathematical description of real-time computations for processing the seismic signal from an accelerometer with three mutually orthogonal components. Data products are generated following published algorithms and should be suited for earthquake early warning (EEW) *as well as* post-disaster recovery and to further situational awareness immediately after an earthquake.

Signal detection and classification serves both categories, magnitude estimation from early P-wave arrivals is essential for EEW. Peak values of particle acceleration, velocity and displacement observed over the full duration of the earthquake are needed to generate maps of shaking intensity for rapid response and post disaster recovery.

Since different author groups have made different proposals to estimate the magnitude of an event from early arrivals of the seismic wave, it is suggested to implement two representative algorithms, based on the approach taken in Japan (Kamigaichi, 2004; Yamamoto et al., 2008; Doi, 2011) (JMA algorithms in the following) and the algorithms developed by Richard Allen's collaborators at the seismological laboratory of the university of California, Berkeley (Berkeley algorithms in the following) (Allen and Kanamori, 2003; Wurman, Allen, and Lombard, 2007; Lockman and Allen, 2007; Wu and Kanamori, 2008; Brown et al., 2011; Kuyuk and Allen, 2013a). The method of Cua and Heaton, 2007 is based on observation of peak acceleration and displacement values which are also valuable in a disaster mitigation context.

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All presented algorithms will perform computations with double precision floating point numbers and an initial conversion may be necessary. Physical units for the acceleration input time-series are cm/s^2 .

2 Filters for signal conditioning

2.1 Filter for JMA algorithm

The JMA algorithms require acceleration time series from each orthogonal channel to be filtered by a finite impulse response (FIR) filter. According to Shabestari and Yamazaki, 2001; Davenport, 2001; Campbell and Bozorgnia, 2011 this filter is constructed in frequency domain from the amplitude spectrum of three filters:

$$F(f) = F_1(f) \cdot F_2(f) \cdot F_3(f) \quad (1)$$

With frequency f given in Hertz,

$$F_1(f) = (1/f)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

$$F_2(f) = (1 + 0.694y^2 + 0.241y^4 + 0.0557y^6 + 0.00966y^8 + 0.00134y^{10} + 0.000155y^{12})^{-1/2}, \quad (3)$$

$$F_3(f) = (1 - \exp(-(f/f_0)^3))^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

Above $y = f/f_c$, and $f_c = 10[Hz]$ is the low-pass cut-off frequency, $f_0 = 0.5[Hz]$ is the high-pass cut-off frequency.

The phase of each filter is set to zero. Figure 1 shows the construction of the filter in the frequency domain. A Matlab script for the construction of the FIR filter is given below.

```
%
% Set up JMA FIR filter
% aft. Campbell, Bozorgnia, Earthq. engin. and struct. dynamics 40, 2011
% and Davenport, NZSEE 2001
%
% andreas@arescon.com, 2014-07-06

clear all;

f=linspace(0.1,50,500);

for i=1:500

F1(i)=sqrt(1/f(i));

fc=10.0;

x=f(i)/fc;

F2(i)=1/sqrt(1 + 0.694*x^2 + 0.241*x^4 + 0.0557*x^6 + 0.009664*x^8
```

```

+ 0.00134*x^10+ 0.000155*x^12);

f0=0.5;

F3(i)=sqrt(1-exp(-(f(i)/f0)^3));

F(i)=F1(i)*F2(i)*F3(i);

end

loglog(f,F); grid on; xlabel('Hz'); ylabel('Amp');

print -depsc2 'JMA_FIR.eps'

```


Figure 1: From Davenport, 2001, construction of JMA FIR

It is suggested that this FIR filter is applied on-line, continuously to each of the three acceleration channels in time domain. The frequency representation thus has to be inverse Fourier transformed. The time domain representation then needs to be windowed to limit the number of time-domain coefficients of the filter to some reasonable number while still maintaining a close approximation the the desired frequency response. Appropriate scaling needs to be applied to assure a 0dB response at 1[Hz].

A “reasonable” number N should be less than 100 coefficients to limit the time-delay introduced by the FIR when it is applied as a causal filter in time-domain as

$$z(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} h(k)x(t-k), \quad (5)$$

where $x(t)$ is the input sample, $h(k)$ are the N filter coefficients and $z(t)$ is the filtered output sample.

2.2 Filters for Berkeley Algorithms

The so-called τ_p^{max} and P_d algorithms (Kuyuk and Allen, 2013b) apply a second order (two-pole) $3Hz$ low-pass Butterworth filter to the vertical component time-series. However, the computation of the magnitude related values is based on velocity or displacement input. Prior integration of the acceleration time series to velocity and a second integration to displacements is thus required. A continuous, on-line integration is suggested for all three channels.

Long term stable integration requires the removal of bias (DC offsets) and very low frequency components. Wu and Kanamori, 2005, apply a 0.075 Hz Butterworth high-pass (of unknown order) before each integration stage. A steep transition band and on-line stability of this IIR is essential and filters of orders higher than two should be implemented as cascaded second order systems (CSOS). A fourth order Butterworth filter is suggested. The de-composition of a direct form IIR-filter into a cascade of second order systems can be accomplished with the Matlab signal processing tool-box.

An example for a Butterworth high-pass is given below:

```
% compute coefficients for CSOS
% 0.075Hz Highpass @200 smpls/s
N=4; % fourth order

[B,A] = butter(N,0.075/100,'high');

% pole-zero representation
[Z,P,K]=tf2zp(B,A);

% transform to second order section coefficients
coeff = zp2sos(Z,P,K);
```

Coefficients are returned in the matrix

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} b_0^0 & b_1^0 & b_2^0 & 1 & a_1^0 & a_2^0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ b_0^{k-1} & b_1^{k-1} & b_2^{k-1} & 1 & a_1^{k-1} & a_2^{k-1} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

for each second order system with Transfer function

$$H^i(z) = \frac{b_0^i z + b_1^i z^{-1} + b_2^i z^{-2}}{1 - a_1^i z^{-1} - a_2^i z^{-2}} \quad i = 0, \dots, k-1. \quad (7)$$

The transfer function of the cascaded system is then

$$H(z) = \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} H^i(z). \quad (8)$$

Each filter is implemented as a direct form II set of difference equations:

$$d(n)^i = y^{i-1}(n) - a_1^i d(n-1)^i - a_2^i d(n-2)^i, \quad (9)$$

$$y^i(n) = b_0^i d(n)^i + b_1^i d(n-1)^i + b_2^i d(n-2)^i, \quad (10)$$

$i = 0, \dots, k-1$, with initialization $y^{-1}(n) = x(n)$.

Here $y^{k-1}(n)$ is the filtered output sample, $x(n)$ is the input sample (c.f. Aboagye, 1999).

2.3 Filters for P-wave detection

Experiments with data from the Japanese strong-motion K-Net and KiK-net suggest that amplitudes recorded from regional earthquakes, relevant for P-wave detection are well represented with spectral components below $10Hz$. Bias (the DC component) and very low frequency components should be removed from the signals as well.

A $0.075Hz$ high-pass, cascaded with a $10Hz$ low pass filter should be used to condition all three acceleration channels for P-wave detection. The type of filter should be a fourth order Butterworth, in a CSOS implementation as discussed before in section 2.2.

3 Integration

The necessary on-line integrations, acceleration to velocity, velocity to displacement are implemented with the trapeze-rule in discrete time domain:

$$y(n) = \frac{\delta t}{2}(x(n) + x(n-1)) + y(n-1), \quad (11)$$

with $x(n)$ being the input-, $y(n)$ the output-sample and δt the sampling time interval.

4 P- and S-wave Detection

4.1 Polarization Analysis

The detection of P-wave arrivals is based on particle motion analysis by means of an on-line singular value decomposition (SVD) update algorithm (Rosenberger, 2010).

If a single three component data sample is seen as a data vector

$$d_n = \begin{bmatrix} z_n \\ x_n \\ y_n \end{bmatrix},$$

where $n = t/\delta t$ is the sample index at time t , δt is the sample interval and z is assumed to be the vertical component, one can construct a data matrix for index n as

$$X_n = \begin{bmatrix} z_0 & z_1 & \dots & z_n \\ x_0 & x_1 & \dots & x_n \\ y_0 & y_1 & \dots & y_n \end{bmatrix} = [d_0 \dots d_n] \quad (12)$$

The SVD of X_n can be viewed as diagonalizing the $3 \times (n + 1)$ matrix X_n through left and right orthogonal transformations as

$$U_n^T X_n V_n = \Sigma_n = \text{diag}(\sigma_0, \dots, \sigma_{k-1}). \quad (13)$$

In this particular case the data matrix has a maximum rank of 3 and $\Sigma_n = \text{diag}(\sigma_i)$ has, at most, three nonzero singular values σ_i . U_n has dimensions 3×3 and V_n is a $(n + 1) \times 3$ matrix.

Only the matrix U_n and the singular values σ_i are required for polarization analysis, matrix V_n is not needed.

The angle (from vertical) of the direction of particle motion is

$$\phi = \arccos(\|u_p[0]\|), \quad (14)$$

where $u_p[0]$ is the first component of the principal left singular vector. A measure for the degree of linear polarization is the ratio of the two largest singular values

$$r = \sigma_1/\sigma_0. \quad (15)$$

Both, angle of incidence and linearity will be used to filter the three component signal for the detection of P-wave arrivals. P-waves show a small incidence angle and exhibit approximately linear polarization.

Key for an efficient implementation is the following procedure which allows to update the solution when a new data vector d_n becomes available without recomputing the full SVD of the augmented data matrix:

$$\begin{aligned} X_n &= [X_{n-1} \quad d_n] \\ &= [(U_{n-1}\Sigma_{n-1}V_{n-1}^T) \quad d_n] \end{aligned}$$

The update procedure starts by projecting the new data vector onto the current orthogonal basis U_{n-1}

$$m = U_{n-1}^T d_n \quad (16)$$

and the subspace orthogonal to U_{n-1}

$$p = (\mathbb{I} - U_{n-1}U_{n-1}^T)d_n, \quad (17)$$

where \mathbb{I} is the identity matrix. The update then takes the form

$$X_n = [(U_{n-1}\Sigma_{n-1}V_{n-1}^T \quad d_n)] \quad (18)$$

$$= \begin{bmatrix} U_{n-1} & \frac{p}{\|p\|} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{n-1} & m \\ 0 & \|p\| \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_{n-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (19)$$

$$= \hat{U}_n Q_n \hat{V}_n^T \quad (20)$$

In the non-stationary case, for data where polarization varies over time, the vector p , orthogonal to the subspace spanned by U_{n-1} at time index $n - 1$, represents new information, a change in the data from the previous state not yet represented by the current subspace base.

Additionally, a sliding exponential window with a (effective) length of N samples is imposed on the data to focus the solution on current values of the data matrix rather than accumulate a mean from the very beginning of the time series.

This is achieved by the introduction of a factor $\lambda = \frac{N-1}{N}$ into the update of the middle matrix in equation 19 as

$$Q_n = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda \Sigma_{n-1} & m \\ 0 & \|p\| \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

The principal vector in the updated U_n , the vector associated with the largest singular value in Σ_n , now points to an exponentially weighted mean direction of particle motion over an effective window of the last N samples.

If the innovation $\|p\|$ is smaller than the instrument's noise floor one may discard p from equation 19 and perform a rank preserving update

$$X_n = [U_{n-1}] [\lambda \Sigma_{n-1} \quad m] \begin{bmatrix} V_{n-1} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (22)$$

The updated matrices \hat{U}_n and \hat{V}_n are orthonormal and Q_n is diagonal with an additional end column vector. If Q_n is diagonalized as $Q_n = A\Omega B^T$, the final update equation becomes

$$X_n = \hat{U}_n A \Omega B^T \hat{V}_n^T. \quad (23)$$

Any suitable algorithm for the diagonalization of an upper triangular matrix can be used to compute

$$A Q_n B^T = \Sigma_n \quad (24)$$

and the update

$$U_n = \hat{U}_n A. \quad (25)$$

Column vectors in U_n and singular values may have to be permuted so that the singular values $\sigma_0, \sigma_1, \sigma_2$ are in descending order of magnitude. With $\|p\|$ of significant size and a rank increasing update according to Eq. 19, a rank reduction, retaining the first two column vectors of U_n and the first two singular values in Σ_n is carried out after the updates of Eqs. 24 and 25 have been computed.

An update for V_n is not required.

The algorithm is initialized by setting

$$U_0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\mathbf{d}_0}{\|d_0\|} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

and

$$\Sigma_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \|d_0\| & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

The Matlab/Octave code below outlines the basic computations using a generic SVD for the diagonalization of Q_n .

```

U=zeros(3,2);
S=zeros(2,2);

for i = 1:M % main loop
    d = [Z(i);N(i);E(i)]; % construct data vector

% simple initialization =====
if(i == 1)
    n2d=norm(d,2);

    U(:,1)=d/n2d; % Eq. 26
    S(1,1)=n2d; % Eq. 27
end
% =====

m = U'*d; % m || U, Eq. 16

m_p = d - U*m; % projection _| U, Eq. 17

r=d'*d;
s=m'*m;
t=U*m;

% Innovation
pp = r - 2*s + t'*t;

if(abs(pp) < SMALL) % instrument noise level
    pp=0;
end

p=sqrt(pp);

if ( p > 0 )
% with rank increase Q: 3x3, Eq. 19
    Q=[lambd*S,m;0,0,p];
else
% rank preserving Q: 2x3, Eq. 22
    Q=[lambd*S,m;0,0,0];
end

% standard generic SVD for the diagonalization of Q, Eq. 24
[A, Ss, V]=svd(Q);

% Updating S and U:
S=Ss(1:2,1:2); % discard smallest singular value

if ( p > 0 )
    U=[U,m_p/p]*A(1:3,1:2); % rank reduction
else
    U=U*A(1:2,1:2); % rank preserving
end

re=1.0;
if(S(1,1) > 0)
    re=S(2,2)/S(1,1); % recti-linearity
end

incl=abs(U(1,1)); % Eq. 29, cos(incl) would be the angle of incidence vs. Z in radians

end % end main loop

```

4.2 Polarization Filter

Every three component input vector d_n is first projected over the rank reduced (3x2) matrix U_n

$$r_n = U_n U_n^T d_n \quad (28)$$

and filter operators are constructed as

$$I_n = \|u_p[0]\| \quad (29)$$

where $u_p[0]$ is the first component of the left principal singular vector (the singular vector associated with the largest singular value) in U_n .

$$R_n = 1 - \sigma_1/\sigma_0 \quad (30)$$

I_n will be close to one for particle motion with a small incidence angle (from vertical) which is characteristic for P-wave arrivals. Transversal S-wave particle motion will be characterized by $I_n \rightarrow 0$, both body wave-types are in theory linearly polarized, thus $R_n \rightarrow 1$.

The polarization filter produces two (3c) output signals:

$$p_n = I_n \cdot R_n \cdot r_n \quad (31)$$

and

$$s_n = (1 - I_n) \cdot R_n \cdot r_n \quad (32)$$

The time series from Eq. 31 contains enhanced P-wave amplitudes while Eqn. 32 produces a time series where S-waves are emphasized. An example is shown in Fig.4.2.

The polarization attributes for P- and S-waves should be computed with **two independent on-line SVDs** so that different time constants for the "forgetting" factor λ can be used for P- and S-waves. P-wave detection in general works best with a nominal time window of 1 second ($\lambda = 199/200 = 0.9950$ for $\delta t = 0.005s$), S-wave detection generally requires a time window of ≈ 5 s, ($\lambda = 0.9990$). Both time windows should be *configurable parameters* so that algorithms can be tuned.

4.3 Detection

Transient signals are detected with a *Short time average, Long time average ratio* (STA/LTA) detector (Allen, 1982; Küpperkoch, Meier, and Diehl, 2012). A moving average of the signal $y(t)$ at time t is approximated as

$$\bar{y}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=t-N+1}^{t-1} y(i) + y(t) \right) \quad (33)$$

$$\approx \frac{N-1}{N} \bar{y}(t-1) + \frac{1}{N} y(t) \quad (34)$$

$$= \alpha \bar{y}(t-1) + (1-\alpha) y(t), \quad (35)$$

Figure 2: The signal is filtered by particle motion attributes, both P- (red) and S-wave components (blue) are plotted together.

with $\alpha = \frac{N-1}{N}$, where $N = \Delta T/\delta t$ is the window size in samples, ΔT the corresponding window length in seconds and δt is the sampling time interval.

The characteristic function of the STA/LTA detector is computed as the ratio of two moving averages with different time window lengths ΔT as configurable parameters.

$$S(t) = \frac{\bar{y}(t)_{\Delta T_{short}}}{\bar{y}(t)_{\Delta T_{long}}} \quad (36)$$

Thresholding $S(t)$ with a configurable value provides the detection. The short and long time windows ΔT_{short} and ΔT_{long} are also coded as configurable parameters.

4.3.1 P-wave Detection

For the detection of P-waves all three components of the signal vector

$$p_n = \begin{bmatrix} p_n[0] \\ p_n[1] \\ p_n[2] \end{bmatrix}$$

from Eq.31 are squared and summed

$$y_p(t) = p_n[0]^2 + p_n[1]^2 + p_n[2]^2 \quad (37)$$

$y_p(t)$ is then subjected to an STA/LTA detector according to Eq.35. Typical values for the short time and long time windows are 2 seconds and 6 seconds respectively.

Additionally the principal singular value σ_0 provides a characteristic function. A threshold in the order of 10 times the normal noise level provides an additional means to detect the P-wave arrival.

Reported is the time-stamp (0.01 s accuracy) and the detected wave type.

4.3.2 S-wave Detection

For the detection of S-waves all three components of the signal from Eq.32 are used for the computation of the STA/LTA characteristic function (Eq.35).

$$y_s(t) = s_n[0]^2 + s_n[1]^2 + s_n[2]^2 \quad (38)$$

Typical values for the short time and long time windows are 4 seconds and 12 seconds respectively.

Reported is the time-stamp (0.01 s accuracy) and the detected wave type.

5 Waveform Parameters

5.1 Berkeley τ_p

The description of the *predominant period* parameter τ_p largely follows Brown et al., 2011.

The acceleration and velocity timeseries of the vertical component signals are needed in the on-line computation of

$$\tau_p(i) = 2\pi\sqrt{\frac{X(i)}{D(i)}}, \quad (39)$$

$$X(i) = \alpha X(i-1) + v(i)^2 \quad (40)$$

$$D(i) = \alpha D(i-1) + a(i)^2 \quad (41)$$

$v(i)$ and $a(i)$ are the velocity and acceleration values at sample index i respectively. Brown et al., 2011 give the "smoothing parameter" as $\alpha = 1.0 - \delta t$, where δt is the sampling time interval (in seconds). This computation is valid for all suitable physical units of velocity and acceleration, but obviously prone to overflow errors. It is suggested that acceleration is scaled to cm/s^2 prior to integration and evaluation of equation 39. The acceleration time series should be band-limited with the IIR filters from Section 2.2 before integration.

The parameter to report is τ_p^{max} , the maximum τ_p value from the observation of 4 seconds of data starting 1.0 second *after* the detection of a P-wave arrival. The 1 second "black-out" window is supposed to allow transients to decay. Both time values should be coded as configurable parameters for the algorithm since there is a considerable variety in what different authors recommend.

Independent of the desired observation time interval, the calculation of τ_p^{max} must terminate with the S-wave arrival.

5.2 Berkeley P_d

According to Kuyuk and Allen, 2013b observation of the *vertical component peak displacement amplitude* of the P-wave is a measure for the relative Magnitude of an event. Physical units are centimetres.

Reported is the *absolute* maximum displacement value, determined from observation of displacement over 4 seconds *immediately* after the P-wave onset. Double integration from acceleration to displacement requires the high- and low-pass filters as described in section 2.2 applied to acceleration and velocity before integration to displacement.

Independent of the desired observation time interval, the calculation of P_d must terminate with the S-wave arrival.

5.3 JMA Instrumental Intensity

The following is largely compiled from (Shabestari and Yamazaki, 2001; Kamigaichi, 2004; Sokolov, Furumura, and Wenzel, 2010; Campbell and Bozorgnia, 2011).

Each channel of acceleration time-series **in units of cm/s^2** is filtered with the FIR filter described in section 2.1 and the vector modulus

$$h_n = \sqrt{z_n^2 + x_n^2 + y_n^2} \quad (42)$$

constructs the new time-series h_n over the time interval of interest, n being the sample index.

In a next step the positive amplitude a_0 has to be determined which satisfies

$$\tau(a_0) = 0.3s, \quad (43)$$

where $\tau(a_0)$ is the total duration of amplitude values exceeding a_0 .

To cast this as an algorithm one computes $h_{max} = \max(h_n)$ and constructs a function

$$w_n(h_n, k) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } h_n \geq h_{max} - k \cdot \delta a \\ 0 & \text{for } h_n < h_{max} - k \cdot \delta a \end{cases}, \quad (44)$$

where δa is the step-size (granularity), $k = 1, \dots, h_{max}/\delta a$, and evaluates

$$s(h_n, k) = \sum_{l=0}^n w_l(h_n, k) \cdot \delta t \quad (45)$$

where δt is the sampling time interval.

The calculation starts with the detection of a P-wave arrival, then finds the current maximum amplitude h_{max} and proceeds evaluating Eq. 44 and 45 for each sample h_n with amplitude steps δa and $k = 0, 1, \dots, K_{a_0}$ until $s(h_n, K_{a_0}) \geq 0.3$. The amplitude step-size δa should be coded as configurable parameter, a reasonable default value would be $\delta a = 0.1 \text{ cm/s}^2$.

Reported is the value $a_0 = h_{max} - K_a \cdot \delta a$.

For noise observations the step size should be much smaller; $\delta a \approx 10^{-3} \text{ cm/s}^2$. Due to the algorithm's iterative structure this will trade off against algorithm performance with large signals. In particular with off-shore installations, where the instrument may exhibit some significant tilt, it may also be necessary to remove any bias from the signal to make a_0 representative of the current noise levels. It is suggested to use the 0.075Hz high-pass IIR filter, described in 2.2 for the removal of bias. As long as JMA a_0 is just used to represent noise levels in a heart-beat message, the application of the FIR filter from section 2.1 is not necessary.

A Matlab/Octave code sample for the calculation of a_0 is given below:

```
delta_a=0.1 % step-size cm/s^2

% compute vector mod trace, input data in cm/s^2
H_Data = sqrt(TZ_Data.^2 + TN_Data.^2 + TE_Data.^2);

H_max=max(H_Data); % max value

NLev=H_max/delta_a; % max. number of amplitude levels to test

S=zeros(NLev,1); % pre allocate

k=1;
do % loop over amplitude levels
  for i=1:nsmpl % loop over time-series

    if H_Data(i) >= H_max - k*delta_a
      S(k)+=REC.dt; % accumulate, sampling time interval
    end
  end
end
```

```
k++;  
until S(k-1)>=0.3; % bail out  
  
A_0=H_max -(k-1)*delta_a; % result: JMA intensity amplitude value
```

JMA Intensity amplitude a_0 is reported in 1 second time intervals, starting with the detection of the P-wave and labelled as **P-wave intensity**. With the arrival/detection of the S-wave the calculation is re-started, intensity amplitudes are reported in 1 second time intervals and labelled as **S-wave intensity**.

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